

Safeguarding Academic Values in Times of Crisis: Findings from a LIBER Survey

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LIBER libraries play a crucial role not only in supporting scholarship, but also in upholding the core values that underpin the academic ecosystem, including integrity, transparency, and European solidarity. Yet these values are increasingly under pressure from political, societal, and technological developments, raising important questions about how they are interpreted and enacted in everyday library practice. Drawing on a survey conducted by the LIBER Rights & Values Taskforce, this short article explores the challenges libraries face in this context, as well as the ways in which they respond, highlighting emerging practices and practical approaches within the LIBER community.

Survey design and methodology

The survey was designed as an email questionnaire targeting directors and staff of research libraries within the LIBER network. It combined closed and open-ended questions to capture both structured insights and qualitative perspectives on the role of values in institutional contexts, with a particular focus on integrity, transparency, and European solidarity. In total, the survey received responses from 14 participants, mostly library directors, representing 12 countries across Europe. Respondents were invited to reflect on their institution's guiding principles, provide concrete examples from practice, and identify challenges as well as support needs. The questionnaire required approximately 25 minutes to complete and offered participants the opportunity to elaborate on their responses and to volunteer for a follow-up (online) interview - 5 institutions opted for this. All data were handled with due care for confidentiality, and any institutional references are subject to respondent approval prior to publication.

Core academic values

In response to the survey's inquiry regarding core academic values, openness emerged as a primary guiding principle, appearing in seven different responses across the listed categories. This value is frequently operationalized through open science, open access, and the "open and responsible use of academic information," which libraries use to ensure knowledge remains accessible, neutral, and transparent. Additionally, inclusivity was highlighted by three respondents as a fundamental value, often paired with diversity and the promotion of equal opportunities to ensure that library spaces are welcoming to all. Libraries find these values most important because they serve as the foundation for their role as trusted, value-driven actors that safeguard research integrity and reinforce public trust. By prioritizing openness and inclusivity, institutions aim to create an interface with society that supports the free formation of opinions and protects academic freedom.

Role of libraries in safeguarding academic values

Responding libraries safeguard academic values through a multi-layered approach that includes institutionalizing integrity in mission statements and creating dedicated scholarly communication departments. To mitigate risks such as bias and data misuse, institutions implement practical measures like anonymous hiring tools, proactive privacy officers, and open internal digital environments for staff transparency. Furthermore, libraries utilize internal auditors, conduct annual vulnerability analyses, and provide education in source criticism to navigate technological challenges like AI-generated misinformation. By actively monitoring and blacklisting unreliable publishers, they reinforce their role as trusted actors in the European research landscape.

What can libraries do in a European context?

The respondents expect the LIBER community to support member libraries by serving as a central hub for sharing knowledge and offering practical guidance on integrity and transparency. Many respondents emphasized the need for shared best practices, case studies, and guidance documents to help libraries address common challenges. Specifically, there is a call for the development of sustainable Diamond Open Access models and collective tools to combat the AI-driven misinformation and fake publications. Beyond technical support, LIBER is also seen as a vital advocate for political and moral support, particularly in helping libraries in crisis, to secure for instance regular funding. Overall, libraries seek to strengthen their role as trusted actors through collaborative frameworks, webinars, and working groups that leverage the collective strength of the European research library community.

To conclude, for libraries to remain trusted, values-driven actors, we must transition from individual institutional efforts to a collective European framework of coordination and solidarity.

*For the LIBER Taskforce on Rights and Values - LIBER Strategy 2023-2027
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Read the whole 2023-2027 LIBER Strategy

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LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries) is the voice of Europe's research library community.

Around 420 national, university and other libraries are part of LIBER and our wider network includes goal-oriented partnerships with other organisations in Europe and beyond.

As an association, we value Collaboration and Inclusivity. We have six main aims:

- High-quality services for all users of library and information services
- Intellectual freedom and access to scholarship
- Collaboration with campus, local, national, European and global partners
- Stewardship of collections and institutional resources, in the most appropriate format
- Leadership, innovation and a willingness to embrace opportunities for change
- Inclusivity, equality of opportunity and fulfilment of potential.